

DEPED COMPUTERIZATION PROGRAM IN DISTRICT 9 OF DIVISION OF BATANGAS CITY

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ABSTRACT

Integration and utilization of ICT in education became in demand in today's situation as brought by the pandemic. The changes in the educational landscape led to maximization of the usage of the available digital resources. Thus, the study aimed to assess the implementation of DepEd Computerization Program in District 9 of Division of Batangas City with the end view of proposing an ICT management plan for its effective implementation in the New Normal. Specifically, it described the characteristics of elementary teachers, assessed the extent of utilization of the computer aided instruction, tested its significant relationship with the profile variables, identified the issues and concerns, and proposed an ICT management plan. The study utilized descriptive method of research with the questionnaire as main data gathering instrument supported by the FGD and interview. Respondents were 105 teachers from 11 public elementary schools in the district. Frequency, percentage, weighted mean, Cronbach alpha and Chi-square Test were the statistical tools used to treat and analyzed the data. Results revealed that 60 percent of the respondents were aged 36 years old and above, with 4-5 gadgets available for teaching, and with at least one ICT training attended. Findings indicated that the program was implemented to a moderate extent in terms of objectives, infrastructure provision, program orientation and monitoring and evaluation. Age, highest educational attainment, and number of ICT trainings were found to have some significant relationships to the extent of utilization of computer aided instruction. Internet connectivity, number of computer units, and upgrading of computer system were the common issues and concerns encountered by the elementary teachers affecting program implementation. On the latter part, the researcher proposed an ICT management plan to raise the ICT literacy of the teachers with consideration to their age and assistance in performing teaching related tasks in the New Normal.

Keywords: ICT in Education, Computer Aided Instruction, Descriptive Method, Philippines